

Natural Language Processing concepts and methods revisited

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Abstract

The paper starts with the history of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and revisits the concepts and methods involved in the NLP. It provides overview of different classifiers and language modelling techniques. The paper also lists the different fields where NLP is used and also the software available to carry out NLP.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing; Machine Learning; Text Classification; Language Modelling

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